

APPENDIX for
Quality information Document (QUID)
for the validation of the Copernicus Marine
reanalysis product of the Mediterranean
biogeochemistry
MEDSEA_MULTIYEAR_BGC_006_008
v3.3

Contributors: A. Teruzzi, V. Di Biagio, L. Feudale, G. Bolzon, P. Lazzari, S. Salon, S. Piani, G. Cossarini

OGS

National Institute
of Oceanography
and Applied
Geophysics

Appendix A: Class1 climatological comparison

This appendix provides supplementary information and additional context to support and enhance the content presented in the Quality Information Document (QUID) for the validation of the Copernicus Marine reanalysis product of the Mediterranean biogeochemistry (<https://documentation.marine.copernicus.eu/QUID/CMEMS-MED-QUID-006-014.pdf>).

This Appendix reports the visual comparison for all the model variables. Weekly (grey lines) and overall average (black lines) profiles for the model reanalysis are compared with climatological vertical profiles (red dots for means and dashed lines for standard deviations) for 16 sub-basins of the Mediterranean Sea (as listed in the QUID document). Model averages refer to the period covered by observations (i.e. 1999-2016). Two sets of figures are present: one for chlorophyll, nutrients (nitrate, phosphate, silicate, ammonium) and oxygen variables (Figure A.1-16), and one for carbonate system variables (pCO₂, DIC, ALK, pH; Figures A.17-32).

Figure A.1.

Figure A.2.

Figure A.3.

Figure A.4.

Figure A.5.

Figure A.6.

Figure A.7

Figure A.8

Figure A.9

Figure A.10

Figure A.11

Figure A.12

Figure A.13

Figure A.14

Figure A.15

Figure A.16.

Figure A.17

Figure A.18

Figure A.19.

Figure A.20.

Figure A.21.

Figure A.22.

Figure A.23.

Fig. IV.13.24.

Figure A.25.

Figure A.26.

Figure A.27.

Figure A.28.

Figure A.29.

Figure A.30.

Figure A.31.

Figure A.32.